

Vibrational Properties, Mean-amplitudes and Force-fields of NF_4^+ and NO_4^{3-}

T. S. RAWAT*, B. B. RAIZADA and A. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, D. B. S. College, Dehra Dun-248 001

and

LALJI DIXIT

Analytical Physics Section, I. I. P., Dehra Dun-248 005

Manuscript received 28 April 1979, revised 16 December 1979, accepted 25 August 1980

Principal force-constants for tetrafluoro nitronium cation and tetra-oxo nitronium anion have been calculated using GVFF, UBFF, OVFF and L. J. potential functions. The eigen values, observed experimentally and computed on the basis of model potentials used, are in good agreement. Observed spectra of the ions were also tried as an inverse eigen value problem using various kinematical models. Mean amplitudes of vibration at $T=0^\circ\text{K}$ to $T=1000^\circ\text{K}$ have been reported for bonded and non-bonded distances and a comparative study of bond properties of N-F and N-O bonds has been presented.

A series of spectroscopic investigations by infrared and Raman techniques appeared in the literature for NF_4^+ cation soon after the discovery of its existence by Christe *et al*¹. Some of the authors²⁻⁵ have reported the GVFF values of the ion following the method adopted by Sawodny *et al*⁴ using the spectral frequencies reported by Christe³. However, the method used for such calculations was criticized by Russian authors⁶ during recent years. Martin Jansen⁶ has detected some of the vibrations of orthonitrates and compared them with the vibrations of tetra fluoro nitronium ion. It was found that δ -sym. $\nu_2(\text{E})=488\text{ cm}^{-1}$, observed in the Raman spectra by Christe³, which remained questioned till to-date was found at 437 cm^{-1} by Martin⁶ and similarly other bonds of NF_4^+ viz $\nu_1(\text{A}_1)=813\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_3(\text{F}_2)=1159\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_4(\text{F}_2)=611\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reported by Christe were observed respectively at 843, 1160 or 1150 and 604 cm^{-1} did not show much deviations from original observation. On the other hand, the spectra observed for NO_4^{3-} ion by Martin⁶, was reported for the first time. Although, Ferraro and co-workers⁷ had done a systematic study of force-fields of almost all tetrahedral compounds and ions known up to 1973 but unfortunately these two ions (NF_4^+ and NO_4^{3-}) could not be studied by Ferraro *et al* and hence a general description of the vibrational properties of these ions seems to be most demanding and our interest lies principally in this study by computing :

- (i) Intramolecular forces and mean amplitudes of thermal vibrations at higher temperatures.
- (ii) To seek co-relation in the vibrational properties of their isoelectronic sequences i.e., BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- , CF_4 and NF_4^+ and finally-
- (iii) The properties of N-F and N-O bonds in systems till studied.

Method of Computation :

We have successfully utilized the methods used so far by Ferraro *et al*⁷ in their study of over 140 tetrahedral systems, viz. GVFF, UBFF, OVFF, L. J. potential method of mutual convertibility of GVFF into OVFF and kinematical approximations⁸ like $L_{12} = \text{O}$, $L_{21} = \text{O}$, P.E.D. and $F_{12} = \text{O}$ whose relevant theories for tetrahedral systems are well known for normal coordinate analysis. Unlike Ferraro *et al* no iteration term has been suppressed in the solution of second order cases of F_2^- species of NF_4^+ and NO_4^{3-} ions and most general forms of P-E functions are taken in kinematically defined methods⁹. It was noticed that the two ions in question belonged to a class where $m_x < m_y$ showing strongly coupled vibrations of $\nu_4(\text{F}_2)$ and $\nu_3(\text{F}_2)$ [for details of definitions of strongly coupled vibrations see the original text¹⁰] and hence there is no surety of validity of even a well defined potential energy function⁷ or an approximation method⁸ due to the reason of high kinematical coupling term (T) which is equal to $\frac{m_x}{m_y}$ or $G_{34}|\det^{\frac{1}{2}}G|$ of their F_2^- species i.e., if G-matrix of NF_4^+ and NO_4^{3-} ions be written as :

$$G_{33} = \frac{4}{3}\mu_x + \mu_y$$

$$G_{34} = -\frac{2}{3}\mu_x \text{ and } G_{44} = \frac{1}{3}\mu_x + 2\mu_y$$

(where μ_x and μ_y are the reciprocal masses of the X-atom and Y-atom respectively).

Then the mass coupling term T is significantly high and under these conditions the mass coupling of $\nu_3(\text{F}_2)$ and $\nu_4(\text{F}_2)$ is strong. Under these circumstances the solution of Wilson's secular equation $|FG - \lambda E| = 0$ is always doubtful and yet no suitable

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED FREQUENCIES OF F_2 SPECIES IN cm^{-1} FOR NF_2^+ AND NO_2^+ IONS

Force-Field	NF_2^+						NO_2^+					
	Observed		Calculated		% deviation		Observed		Calculated		% deviation	
	ν_3	ν_4	ν_3	ν_4	ν_3	ν_4	ν_3	ν_4	ν_3	ν_4	ν_3	ν_4
	1160						1012	699				
	1150	604	—	—	—	—	988	651	—	—	—	—
UBFF	—	—	1103.5	701.8	5	16	—	—	926	783.8	8.5	17
			1092	703	5	16			1017	604	3	7
OVFF			1108	695	4.5	15			1017.9	660	0.58	1.3
			1199	696	4	15			992	644.7	0.40	0.9
OVFF (A=6.5 B/R)			1108.7	694.6	4.4	15			1021.7	654	0.96	2
			1096.6	696	4.6	15			987	644.5	0.00	0.97
GVFF (from OVFF)			1108	695	4.5	15			1017.9	660	0.58	1.3
			1097	696	4.6	15			988.6	648.9	0.0	1.0

solution exists for F_2 doubly degenerate vibrations. Hence we have tried several methods to solve the problem of (2×2) F_2 species in these ions.

Cyvin's secular equation $^{10(a)}|\Sigma G^{-1} - \Delta E| = 0$ was solved in order to examine vibrational properties of bonds at various temperatures using $L_{12} = 0$ approximation method¹¹. Keeping in view that it is a reasonable method¹² to compute symmetrized mean square amplitude matrices (Σ) from 0°K to 1000°K. The final mean amplitudes of vibration for bonded N-F, N-O and non-bonded F...F and O...O distances were evaluated using standard expressions from Cyvin^{10(a)}.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the frequency reproduction of doubly degenerate antisymmetric stretching and deformation vibration ν_3 and ν_4 respectively by utilizing various potential energy function models. Out of these the best frequency reproduction from computed force constants was found in the case of OVFF model presumably because of the fact that it accounts for the correct picture of non-bonded forces in the case of these ions.

 TABLE 2—SYMMETRIZED FORCE-CONSTANTS ($\text{mdyn}/\text{\AA}$) AND GVFF CONSTANTS ($\text{mdyn}/\text{\AA}$) FOR NF_2^+ AND NO_2^+ IONS

(A) Symmetrized force constants	NF_2^+ Method	NF_2^+		
		$F_{33}(F_2)$	$F_{34}(F_2)$	$F_{44}(F_2)$
$F_{11} = 7.954$ $F_{22} = 0.712$	$L_{21} = 0$	10.821	4.239	2.103
		10.636	4.166	2.074
	$L_{12} = 0$	6.843	1.149	0.892
		6.750		
	P.E.D.	5.362	0.575	0.892
		5.270		
	MVFF	5.437	0.000	0.419
		5.402	0.000	0.402
	UBFF	4.555	0.547	1.116
		4.514	0.561	
	OVFF	5.153	0.621	0.993
		5.105	0.633	0.989
OVFF (A=6.5 B/R)	5.161	0.621	0.991	
	5.102	0.634	0.989	

(Table 2(A) Contd.)

GVFF (from OVFF)	5.153	0.621	0.993
	5.105	0.633	0.989
NO_2^+ $L_{21} = 0$	7.013	2.640	1.515
	6.685	2.516	1.441
$L_{12} = 0$	5.219	1.154	0.956
	4.966	1.092	0.905
P.E.D.	3.826	0.577	0.956
	3.647	0.547	0.905
MVFF	4.791	0.000	0.220
	4.550		0.212
UBFF	4.271	0.644	0.867
	4.025	0.642	0.845
OVFF	3.385	0.771	1.239
	3.624	0.722	1.044
OVFF (A=6.5 B/R)	3.250	0.766	1.278
	3.448	0.722	1.086
GVFF (from OVFF)	3.385	0.771	1.239
	3.594	0.722	1.044

TABLE 2(B)

GVFF Constants NF_2^+					
Method	fr	frr	$f_{\alpha} - f_{\alpha\alpha}$	$f_{\alpha} - f'_{\alpha\alpha}$	$f_{r\alpha} - f'_{r\alpha}$
$L_{21} = 0$	10.105	0.717	1.408	2.103	2.997
	9.966	0.670	1.393	2.074	2.946
$L_{12} = 0$	7.121	0.278	0.802	0.892	0.813
	7.051	0.301			
P.E.D.	6.010	6.648			
	5.941	0.671	0.802	0.892	0.406
MVFF	5.582	0.791	0.466	0.221	0.000
	6.151	0.851	0.462	0.212	
GVFF Constants NO_2^+					
Method	fr	frr	$f_{\alpha} - f_{\alpha\alpha}$	$f_{\alpha} - f'_{\alpha\alpha}$	$f_{r\alpha} - f'_{r\alpha}$
$L_{21} = 0$	6.935	0.0787	1.216	1.515	1.867
	6.688	0.003	1.113	1.441	1.779
$L_{12} = 0$	5.589	0.370	0.936	0.956	0.816
	5.399	0.433	0.845	0.905	0.772
P.E.O.	4.544	0.718	0.936	0.956	0.406
	4.410	0.763	0.845	0.905	
MVFF	5.268	0.477	0.560	0.220	0.000
	5.087	0.537	0.499	0.212	

Table 2 lists the symmetry force constants of NF_2^+ and NO_2^+ ions based on several models. Our values for symmetry force constants are slightly modified to those reported earlier by Christe *et al.*²

The values of $\nu_2(E)$ symmetry class due to Christie *et al* are not at all reliable owing to ambiguous assignment of frequency $\nu_2(E)$ while the values reported by us do not suffer this lacuna. A general outcome from this table is $F_{11}(F_2)$ from several methods varies in the order: $L_{21}=O > L_{12}=O > MVFF > UBFF > P. E. D. > OVFF > OVFF \left(A=6.5 \frac{B}{R} \right) > GVFF$ (from OVFF) and OFF diagonal force constants F_{ij} also follow the same trend. In general F^s of NF_4^+ $>$ F^s of NO_2^- . Valence force constants fr NF_4^+ $>$ fr NO_2^- showing the higher stability of N-F bond than N-O bond. Also $f_{\alpha\alpha} - f_{\alpha\alpha}$ NF_4^+ $>$ $f_{\alpha\alpha} - f_{\alpha\alpha}$ NO_2^- indicating that angle bending force constant is a function of the mass of ligand atom. Thus it may be said that in the ionic species like NF_4^+ and NO_2^- , the strength of bond is a function of the oxidation states of F and O. It is interesting to compare the valence force-constants in the series of iso-electronic sequences of NF_4^+ and NO_2^- .

The ion NF_4^+ is iso-electronic with BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- and CF_4 . According to Woodward¹³ the force-constants of iso-electronic sequences increase as the positive charge on central atom increases in the family of single bond systems. So the stretching force-constants¹⁴⁻¹⁵ fr (BeF_4^{2-}) = 3.17 mdyne/Å $<$ fr (BF_4^-) = 4.41 mdyne/Å $<$ fr (CF_4) = 6.70 mdyne/Å $<$ fr (NF_4^+) = 10.10 mdyne/Å ($L_{21}=O$ method) follows Woodward's ruling. However, fr values deduced by other methods such as $L_{12}=O$, MVFF, P.E.D. of NF_4^+ are taken into consideration, they disobey the Woodward ruling and even the most authentic force-fields of tetrahedral ions viz. OVFF and UBFF are not capable enough to cope with Woodward's theory because K_1 NF_4^+ (OVFF) = 3.9 mdyne/Å or 3.84 mdyne/Å and K NF_4^+ (UBFF) = 3.46 mdyne/Å are less than the stretching force constant fr = 6.70 mdyne/Å of CF_4 . So we dare say that all the above mentioned methods are inadequate to describe the correct nature of intramolecular forces of NF_4^+ ion. Thus the isoelectronic series BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- , CF_4 and NF_4^+ violates the Woodward theory so far as stretching force constant of each member is concerned. Since fr values of BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- and CF_4 were determined by independent workers and follows Woodward pattern; hence amongst the fr values of NF_4^+ , deduced here by various methods, only those obeying Woodward's rule, should be treated as reliable and others must be discarded so that the uniqueness of the force-fields for BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- and CF_4 determined by individual workers may remain compatible with NF_4^+ .

Further, according to Woodward¹³ the trends of fr and F_{11} would be increasing with decreasing M-F bond length as the ionic charge varies from -2 to +1 and to some extent this is true¹⁴. Since $R(Be-F)$ = 1.56 Å $<$ $R(C-F)$ = 1.30 Å. Hence covalent M-F bond strength increases in the series from BeF_4^{2-} to NF_4^+ . But this was not the case as

indicated in the study of the Christie *et al*³, who showed that it decreases from CF_4 to NF_4^+ . Christie *et al*³ observed that the valence force constants of NF_4^+ are greater than the valence force constants of NF_3 because of the difference in the number of free electron pairs on the bonding atom pairs. It is not as great as it should be according to Woodward's prediction and inferred that fr values of NF_4^+ are underestimated. However, our computed values fulfil this gap i.e., rate of increase of bond stretch force constant fr from BeF_4^{2-} to NF_4^+ is a linear function of charge on the ions. Taking fr to be 10.10 mdyne/Å (NF_4^+) and Siebert's single bond value¹⁶ f_1 = 7.09, the bond order for N-F in NF_4^+ comes out to be 1.40 Å and in general for this series the bond order $n = fr/f_1$ varies as: 1.04 Å for BeF_4^{2-} $<$ 1.13 Å for CF_4 $<$ 1.40 Å for NF_4^+ $>$ 1.03 Å for NF_3 . Christie *et al*³ calculated bond order for NF_4^+ to be 0.85 Å and anticipated this decrease less than 1 Å to the considerable polarisation of N-F bond in NF_4^+ caused by the positive formal charge on the nitrogen atom bonded to highly electronegative fluorine atom. What we feel to emphasize is that the bond order of each member will be always greater than 1, whatever electro positive central atom be taken, under the influence of highly electronegative fluorine atom. Because in the valence shell of each central atom of this isoelectronic sequence there will be a maximum of 8 electrons and consequently if the bonding orbitals of central atom have the same hybridization states, so much decrease of bond order would not result due to more polarisation effect of electronegative fluorine.

In the isoelectronic sequence BeF_4^{2-} , BF_4^- , CF_4 and NF_4^+ , the repulsion force constant F is expected to depend on F...F (non-bonded) distance and to decrease as F...F distance increases. $F(BeF_4^{2-})$ = 0.48 mdyne/Å, $F(BF_4^-)$ = 1.06 mdyne/Å and $F(NF_4^+) = 1.12$ mdyne/Å. Similarly with the difference of electronegativity between Be and F, B and F, C and F and N and F, the stretching force constant fr decrease:

	fr
BeF_4^{2-}	1.40 mdyne/Å
BF_4^-	2.46 mdyne/Å
CF_4	4.59 mdyne/Å
NF_4^+	10.10 mdyne/Å

The computed values of force-constants of $NO_2^+(a)$, NO_2^{17} and NO_2^- are as under:

	NO_2	NO_2^+	NO_2^-
fr	12.309	5.72	6.93
H	1.10	0.79	0.61

In the above NO_2 series the molecular species NO_2 gives high magnitudes of stretching force-constant

and in ionic species NO_3^- and NO_2^- corresponding force constants are small because of their typical ionic structures.

Mean amplitudes of vibration of NF_4^+ and NO_4^{2+} are listed in Table 4. The mean amplitudes for isoelectronic sequence BeF_4^{2-} , CF_4 , NF_3 , NF_4^+ and NO_x at $T=298^\circ\text{K}$ are as follows :

Species	l_{M-F}	$l_{F...F}$	NO_x series	l_{N-O}	$l_{O...O}$
BeF_4^{2-}	0.0646 ^(1a)	0.1952 ^(1a)	NO	0.0344 ^(10a)	—
CF_4	0.044 ^(1a) 0.0432 ⁽²¹⁾	0.0539 ⁽²¹⁾	NO_2	0.0381 ^(10a)	—
NF_3	0.0436	0.0821	NO_2^-	0.0418 ⁽¹⁷⁾	—
NF_4^+	0.01828 ^(1a)	0.07203 ^(1a)	NO_2^{2-}	0.0415 ⁽²²⁾	0.0191 ⁽²²⁾
				0.0736	0.0863

TABLE 3—OVFF AND UBFF CONSTANTS (MDYN/Å) FOR NF_4^+ AND NO_4^{2+} IONS

Ion	$k_1(k)$	$k'_{\alpha}(3H)$	A(F/2)	B/R(-F')
NF_4^+	3.910	1.047	0.505	0.079
	3.837	1.029	0.514	0.079
	(3.462)	(0.712)	(0.562)	(0.303)
	(3.476)	(0.719)	(0.560)	(0.299)
	3.919*	1.052*	0.504*	0.078*
NO_4^{2+}	3.834	1.028	0.515	0.079
	1.844	1.477	0.607	0.057
	2.180	1.180	0.565	0.046
	(2.983)	(1.856)	(0.464)	(-0.037)
	(2.778)	(1.332)	(0.490)	(0.045)
1.717*	1.408*	0.622*	0.096*	
2.002	1.092	0.587	0.090	

Value in parentheses indicates UBFF Constants

*A=6.5 B/R

TABLE 4—MEAN AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION (in Å) FOR NF_4^+ AND NO_4^{2+} IONS

Temp	NF_4^+		NO_4^{2+}	
	l_{x-y}	$l_{y...y}$	l_{x-y}	$l_{y...y}$
T= 0°K	0.0434	0.0798	0.0686	0.0845
	0.0435	0.0800	0.0711	0.0857
T=298°K	0.0435	0.0821	0.0736	0.0863
	0.0437	0.0823	0.0774	0.0877
T=500°K	0.0452	0.0884	0.0844	0.0926
	0.0454	0.0886	0.0898	0.0946
T=600°K	0.0466	0.0923	0.0901	0.0967
	0.0468	0.0926	0.0961	0.1010
T=700°K	0.0481	0.0964	0.0957	0.1011
	0.0483	0.0967	0.1024	0.1035
T=800°K	0.0506	0.1007	0.1012	0.1056
	0.0508	0.1010	0.1083	0.1079
T=900°K	0.0515	0.1049	0.1062	0.1034
	0.0518	0.1053	0.1141	0.113
T=1000°K	0.0533	0.1095	0.1115	0.1146
	0.0537	0.1099	0.1197	0.1177

This shows that F...F mean amplitudes are in the range of 0.082 Å and O...O mean amplitudes are in the range of 0.086 Å. In the case of different N—O

bonds the mean amplitude values become lower as stretching force constants increase (Case of NO_x). NO has the lowest mean amplitude value because of highest bond order amongst the NO_x family and NO_4^{2-} has the highest mean amplitude value because of the fact that it possesses delocalisation of π -bonds (as in NO_3^- ion) and excess of formal charge over it. In general mean amplitudes for bonded and non-bonded distances in NF_4^+ and NO_4^{2-} are found to increase smoothly up to 1000° K.

References

- K. O. CHRISTE, J. P. GUERTIN and A. E. PAVLATH, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1966, **2**, 83.
- K. O. CHRISTE and D. PILIPOVICH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2803.
- K. O. CHRISTE, J. P. GUERTIN, A. E. PAVLATH and W. SAWODNY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 533.
- W. SAWODNY, A. FADINI and K. BALLEIN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 995.
- B. S. AVERBUKH, L. S. MAYANT and G. B. SHALTUYER, *J. Mol. Spectry.*, 1969, **30**, 310.
- MARTIN JANSEN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 534.
- L. S. BASILE, J. R. FERRARO, P. LABONVILLE and M. C. WALL, S. M. C., *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **11**, 21.
- A. MULLER, R. KEBABCIOGLU, S. J. CYVIN and N. MOHAN, Det Kongelige Norske Videnskabers Selskab Skrifter No. 7, 1972.
- T. SHIMANOCHI, The Model Force-fields in Physical Chemistry in Advance Treatise, Edited by Eyring, Henderson and Jost, (Academic Press, New York), 1970.
- A. J. P. ALIX, S. N. RAI and J. N. RAI, *Indian J. Pure & Appl. Phys.*, 1976, **14**, 639.
- (a) S. J. CYVIN, "Molecular Vibrations & Mean Square Amplitudes, Elsevier, Oslo, 1968.
- A. MULLER, *Z. Phys. Chem. Leipzig.*, 1968, **238**, 116.
- S. J. CYVIN, B. N. CYVIN and A. MULLER, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1969, **4**, 341.
- L. A. WOODWARD, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 1271.
- A. S. QUIST, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1, 79, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **54**, 4896.
- B. KREBS, A. MULLER and A. FADINI, *J. Mol. Spectry.*, 1967, **24**, 198.
- H. SIEBERT, *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.* 1953, **273**, 170.
- C. J. PEACOCK, A. MULLER and R. KEBABCIOGLU, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1968, **2**, 163.
- A. N. PANDEY, B. B. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. DUBLESH and A. MULLER, *Indian J. Pure & Appl. Phys.*, 1973, **11**, 782.
- K. RAMASWAMY and N. MOHAN, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1969, **43**, 693.
- A. MULLER and S. J. CYVIN, *J. Mol. Spectry.*, 1968, **26**, 315.
- P. C. SARKAR, G. C. SINGH and (Km.) S. ROY CHOUDHURY, *Acta Physica Polonica*, 1978, **A53**, 895.
- P. C. SARKAR and G. C. SINGH, *Spectroscopy Letters*, 1977 **10**, 319.